

Complex Formation Between Phenylmercuric Ion and Some Chelating Ligands

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The thermodynamic instability constants of (1:1) complexes of phenylmercuric cation with ferron, oxine and orthophenanthroline were found to be 4.0×10^{-11} , 1.5×10^{-11} and 5.8×10^{-9} respectively at 26°-27°. The extremely small values for the instability constants of these complexes indicate that the ligands possibly behave as chelating agents towards the organomercuric cation.

THE solution chemistry of organomercuric cations have been investigated rather sparingly. Only recently several investigators¹⁻⁶ have studied the complex formation equilibria of some alkyl and aryl mercuric cations. Barbieri *et al.*⁷ have reported the formation of a 1:1 complex of oxine with ethyl and phenylmercuric cations, but stability constants of these complexes have not been reported by them. In the present paper we wish to report the instability constants of the 1:1 complexes of phenylmercuric cation with ferron, oxine and *o*-phenanthroline from spectrophotometric measurements.

Experimental

Phenylmercuric hydroxide was prepared from basic phenylmercuric nitrate by method of Schramm⁸ and purified by recrystallisation from dilute aqueous sodium hydroxide. The sample was stored over solid potassium hydroxide inside a desiccator painted black to prevent photodecomposition. Known amount of phenylmercuric hydroxide was dissolved in chloride free distilled water to give a $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution. $C_6H_5Hg^+$ ion content of the solution was also estimated by direct titration with standard potassium thiocyanate solution (0.01M) using ferric alum indicator. The concentration of $C_6H_5Hg^+$ obtained titrimetrically and from weight agreed within the limits of experimental error. Freshly prepared and estimated solutions of C_6H_5HgOH were used for each set of experiments.

The ligands, *o*-phenanthroline, oxine and ferron were of AR quality and were used as such. Standard solutions of ferron and oxine were prepared by weight. Standard *o*-phenanthroline solution was prepared by dissolving a known amount of the ligand in a slightly more than equivalent amount of standard perchloric acid. Ionic strength was maintained by adding sodium perchlorate prepared from AR perchloric acid and AR sodium hydroxide. All solutions were prepared in double distilled water.

pH measurements were made with a Mareoni pH meter model TF 511d, the glass electrode being

standardised against tetroxalate (pH = 1.68), phthalate (pH = 4.01) and phosphate (pH = 6.86) buffers. pH adjustments were done with freshly prepared 0.01M NaOH or 0.01N perchloric acid solutions. Optical density measurements were made with a Hilger-Watt UVISPEK spectrophotometer model H₇₀₀₋₃₀₃. All optical density measurements were made at room temperature which varied between 25.5°-27°.

Results and Discussion

Let the equilibria involving phenylmercuric hydroxide and the ligands (ferron and oxine) be represented as,

$$K = \frac{x}{(a-x)(b-x)}$$

where $x = [C_6H_5HgOX]$ or $[C_6H_5HgL^-]$; a, b are total concentrations of C_6H_5HgOH and oxine or ferron respectively. The values of 'x' were computed from the relationships,

$$x = \frac{O.D._{ob}}{\epsilon_2 l}$$

(for oxine system, since correction due to absorption of oxine under the experimental conditions was negligible, vide Table 3) and

$$x = \frac{O.D._{obs} - \epsilon_1 bl}{(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1) l}$$

(for ferron system). In the above expressions O.D._{obs} stand for observed optical density of solutions containing C_6H_5HgOH and the ligand, 'ε₁' is the

extinction coefficient of ferron, 'e₂' is that of the ferron or oxine complex and 'l' is the length of the light path.

It was observed that the mixed solutions of *o*-phenanthroline and C₆H₅HgOH absorb strongly around 270 nm. Since the absorbancies (at 270 nm) of such solutions were significantly higher than the sum of the absorbancies due to *o*-phenanthroline and C₆H₅HgOH, interaction between them was indicated. Complex formation between C₆H₅Hg⁺ ion and *o*-phenanthroline was studied spectrophotometrically at 270 nm and the relevant data are given in Table 3.

TABLE 1. STABILITY CONSTANT OF FERRON COMPLEX
Reaction : C₆H₅HgOH + HL⁻ ⇌ C₆H₅HgL⁻ + HgO
λ = 400 nm, l = 3 cm, C₆H₅HgL⁻ = 3629 ± 6,
HL⁻ = 865.8 ± 6.3. Temp. = 26.5°, pH = 4.64,
Ionic Strength = 0.01M.

[Ferron] × 10 ² M	[C ₆ H ₅ HgOH] × 10 ² M	O.D.	K × 10 ⁻⁵
20.0	20.1	0.162	2.9
30.0	30.1	0.259	3.3
35.0	35.2	0.300	2.6
50.0	50.2	0.455	3.3
65.0	65.3	0.588	2.4
70.0	70.3	0.6315	2.1
75.0	75.3	0.685	2.3

K_{A_v} = 2.7 (± 0.2) × 10⁵

TABLE 2. STABILITY CONSTANT OF OXINE COMPLEX

Reaction : C₆H₅HgOH + HOX ⇌ C₆H₅HgOX + H₂O.
λ = 400 nm, l = 3 cm, C₆H₅HgOX = 2174 ± 10
Temp. 27°, pH = 6.90, Ionic Strength = 0.01M

[Oxine] × 10 ² M	[C ₆ H ₅ HgOH] × 10 ² M	O.D.	K × 10 ⁻⁴
83.6	56.2	0.208	2.53
95.5	64.2	0.260	2.95
107.0	72.2	0.307	3.12
119.0	80.2	0.348	3.00
143.0	96.3	0.430	2.81
102.0	64.2	0.2775	3.34

K_{A_v} = 2.96(± 0.12) × 10⁴.

TABLE 3. STABILITY CONSTANT OF *o*-PHENANTHROLINE COMPLEX

Reaction : C₆H₅HgOH + Phen + H⁺ ⇌ C₆H₅HgPhen⁺ + H₂O.
λ = 270 nm, l = 1.0 cm, pH = 6.90, Ionic Strength = 0.01M
a = [Phen] = 2.445 × 10⁻⁶M, d₁ = 0.5515, d₂ = 0.733.
Temp = 25.5°

[C ₆ H ₅ HgOH] × 10 ⁵ M	O.D.	K' × 10 ⁻⁵
1.45	0.627	1.7
2.15	0.669	3.2
2.90	0.687	2.7
3.55	0.695	2.3
4.36	0.703	2.1
5.51	0.713	2.5
11.6	0.732	—
14.5	0.732	—

Considering the acid dissociation constant of *o*-phenanthroline ion (K_{a,phenH⁺} = 1.0 × 10⁻⁵, 25°)⁹ and the high solution instability of coordination number four of Hg(II) in organomercuric complexes it is justified to represent the interaction equilibrium between C₆H₅HgOH and *o*-phenanthroline as,

at pH = 6.90 and in the absence of complexing anions. Assuming f_{H⁺} = f_{C₆H₅Hg⁺}, the thermodynamic equilibrium constant (K) for reaction (3) is given by

$$K = \frac{x}{(a-x)(b-x)[H^+]} = K'/H^+,$$

where x = [C₆H₅HgPhen⁺], a = [Phen]_{total} and b = [C₆H₅HgOH]_{total}. Since *o*-phenanthroline and its complex with phenylmercuric cation are the only absorbing species at (270 nm) in the range of concentrations of C₆H₅HgOH used in the present work, the optical densities of the mixed solutions can be expressed as,

$$d = \epsilon_1(a-x)l + \epsilon_2xl \dots (4)$$

where 'ε₁' and 'ε₂' are the extinction coefficients of *o*-phenanthroline and C₆H₅HgPhen⁺ respectively. The concentration of the complex (x) can be expressed in terms of absorbancies and the concentrations of the ligand (which was kept constant for all measurements) as,

$$x = \frac{d-d_1}{d_2-d_1} \cdot a \dots (5)$$

where d₁ = O.D. of *o*-phenanthroline solution of concentration 'a' and d₂ = O.D. due to C₆H₅HgPhen⁺ of concentration 'a'. d₃ was found out from the data presented in Table 3 by extrapolating the O.D. vs. [C₆H₅HgOH] plot to high concentration of C₆H₅HgOH.

From the knowledge of equilibrium constants (K) of the reactions (1) and (2), pK_{OH} values of ferron¹⁰ (pK_{OH} = 6.46, 2M NaCl, 25°) and oxine¹¹ (pK_{OH} = 10.54, μ = 0, 25°), ionic product of water (K_w = 1.0 × 10⁻¹⁴) and the basic dissociation constant of C₆H₅HgOH¹ (K_b = 1.0 × 10⁻¹⁰, μ = 0, 25°) the instability constants of ferron and oxine complexes

K_{inst} = K_{dHL} · K_b / K · K_w, turn out to be 4.0 × 10⁻¹¹ and 1.5 × 10⁻¹¹ at 25°-27° respectively.

Representing the dissociation equilibrium for the *o*-phenanthroline complex as :

the instability constant for C₆H₅HgPhen⁺ species (K_{inst} = K_b / K_w · K), calculated using the value of the

equilibrium constant of reaction (3) ($K = 1.7 \times 10^{12}$) and $K_w = 1.0 \times 10^{-14}$ and $K_b = 1.0 \times 10^{-10}$, turned out to be 5.8×10^{-9} . The extremely small values for the instability constants for ferron, oxine and o-phenanthroline complexes of $C_6H_5Hg^+$ ion lead us to believe that these ligands behave as chelating agents towards the organomercuric cation.

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